

1 **Multiple causal mechanisms linking biodiversity conservation with human well-**
2 **being**

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15
16 **Figures:**

- 17 1. Illustrative conceptual framework
18 2 Impact typology

19
20 **Tables**

- 21 1. Second tier pathways

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- 24 S1 Definitions of key terms

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26 **Article type:** Analysis
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36

37 **Abstract**

38

39 Sustainability science and sustainable development policies increasingly recognize the contribution of
40 biodiversity conservation to human well-being. However, understanding of the linkages between
41 conservation and human well-being remains limited. Empirical evidence on the existence, magnitude and
42 variation in causal pathways is fragmented, hampering decision-makers' ability to design conservation
43 interventions that also support human well-being. Here we present a conceptual framework that identifies
44 five major pathways through which conservation interventions affect human well-being: 1) governance, 2)
45 ideas and information, 3) conservation infrastructure, 4) ancillary opportunities, and 5) ecosystem services.
46 These pathways may interact, creating novel synergies and trade-offs, scale-dependency, and distributive
47 effects that shape an intervention's social impact. Use of such a multi-causal framework can help avoid
48 skewing policy decisions and investments toward any one pathway. Recognition of the diverse mechanisms
49 linking conservation and human well-being allows scholars and practitioners to better assess the contribution
50 of biodiversity conservation to global sustainability.

51

52

53 Sustainability research and sustainable development policies emphasize a central role for ecosystem services
54 in supporting human well-being¹. Provisioning, regulating, cultural, and supporting services from ecosystems
55 shape the constituents of human well-being, including basic material for a good life, health, security, social
56 relations, and freedom of choice and action ². Recognition of these linkages is increasingly reflected in policies
57 seeking to advance sustainable development³ as well as biodiversity conservation interventions with explicit
58 human well-being goals (e.g., ⁴). The 2015 United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) codified
59 this ecosystem services paradigm³, likely shaping development policies through 2030 and influencing the
60 direction of billions in public and private sector expenditures⁵.

61
62 The spotlight on ecosystem services has left complementary mechanisms linking conservation interventions
63 with human well-being largely overlooked. These alternative mechanisms are frequently identified as
64 exogenous ‘contextual’ factors, but are seldom made explicit in conceptual frameworks (e.g., ⁶) or empirical
65 studies (e.g., ⁷). Just as some decry a narrow focus on a single outcome from policy interventions (or ‘mono-
66 consequentialism’; ⁸), a narrow focus on the role of ecosystem services in human well-being risks misplaced
67 ‘mono-causality’, the erroneous attribution of causality to a single, studied mechanism. Both mono-causality
68 and mono-consequentialism risk distorting research agendas potentially skewing policy decisions to focus on
69 single outcomes, pathways or both.

70
71 Recent studies suggest the existence of diverse pathways linking conservation interventions to human well-
72 being⁸⁻¹⁰ and offer initial evidence about the relative importance of these mechanisms¹¹. However, evidence
73 on the operation of specific mechanisms remains limited because the scientific community lacks the
74 conceptual frameworks and empirical designs needed to underpin mechanistic analyses¹².

75
76 Here, we develop a conceptual framework to analyze the varied mechanisms linking conservation
77 interventions and human well-being. We first discuss the ecosystem services-centered model and its
78 influence on policy and practice. We then introduce a more expansive conceptual framework that highlights
79 the diverse mechanisms by which conservation interventions impact human well-being and illustrate these
80 mechanisms with case-studies. Lastly, we discuss the scientific and policy implications of multi-causal
81 thinking for documenting biodiversity conservation contributions to sustainable development.

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84

85 **Social impacts of biodiversity conservation**

86 Human well-being, defined as “a state of being with others, where human needs are met, where one can act
87 meaningfully to pursue one’s goals, and where one enjoys a satisfactory quality of life”¹³ can be
88 operationalized in many ways¹⁴. Nevertheless, the social impacts (positive, negative or neutral) of
89 conservation interventions are frequently analyzed mono-consequentially⁸, via composite indices (e.g., ¹⁵),
90 that may not reflect local priorities¹⁴ or variation within and among social groups ¹⁴. Empirical evidence
91 suggests conservation affects many human well-being domains ⁹, including wealth (e.g., ¹⁵), health (e.g., ¹⁶),
92 education (e.g., ¹⁷), culture (e.g., ¹⁸), social relationships (e.g., ¹⁹) and subjective well-being (e.g., ¹⁹).

94 **The prevailing paradigm: Ecosystem services**

95 Since the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MEA) in 2005, ecosystem services—the conditions and
96 processes of ecosystems that (help to) generate benefits for people¹—has become the dominant lens for
97 understanding the relationship between biodiversity conservation and human well-being²⁰. The MEA
98 framework catalyzed an extensive research agenda that models (e.g., ²¹), quantifies (e.g., ^{22,23}), and values
99 (e.g., ^{21,24}) ecosystem services as a means to achieve sustainable development. Ecosystem services thinking
100 has structured the development and implementation of international biodiversity conservation (e.g., Aichi
101 Targets 14-16, ⁴) and development (e.g., SDGs; ³) policy, influencing not just what we conserve, but how we
102 conserve it.

104 The rise of ecosystem services to “central metaphor within which to express humanity’s need for the rest of
105 living nature”²⁰ has spurred a variety of frameworks that adopt ecosystem services as a critical link between
106 conservation and human well-being (e.g., ^{1,6,25}). A growing literature documents the magnitude, direction or
107 variation of ecosystem service impacts on human well-being (see ²³), but few studies consider how
108 conservation interventions (e.g., protected areas, PAs) may affect the flow of ecosystem services²⁶.

110 Amid concern that the ecosystem services framework “downplays” other pathways²⁷, social characteristics
111 and processes are increasingly seen as mediators that influence the direction, magnitude and variation in
112 ecosystem service impacts on human well-being. For example, Fisher et al. ²⁵ introduce a framework that
113 places resource access at the center of linkages between ecosystem services and human well-being and
114 importantly, identifies some causal mechanisms (e.g., monetary benefit) as independent social processes,
115 unaffected by ecosystem services provision. Such signs of integration between ecosystem services (e.g., ¹)

116 and the literature on the social impacts of conservation (e.g., ²⁶) are promising, but have yet to coalesce into a
117 coherent multi-causal framework.

118

119 **Conceptualizing links between biodiversity conservation and human well-being**

120 Conservation interventions reshape the ways in which people interact with the environment and each other,
121 producing changes in cognition and behavior, which have impacts on social and ecological conditions. We
122 identify an illustrative set of pathways generated by conservation interventions that may generate a suite of
123 human well-being outcomes (Figure 1). We define a pathway as one or more causal mechanisms that operate
124 via similar ecological or social processes, or share higher-tier properties (e.g., a functional relationship to the
125 intervention itself). These pathways include: a) *governance*; b) the flow of *ideas and information*; c)
126 *infrastructure* associated with the intervention; d) *ancillary opportunities* that may follow from, or coincide
127 with, conservation; and e) *ecosystem services*.

128

129 Causal mechanisms are processes by which an intervention causally affects a specific social or ecological
130 variable, via one or more intermediate variables^{12,28}. This sequence of ‘cogs-and-wheels’²⁸ linking intervention
131 to outcome may be short or long, and operate continuously or sporadically. Individual causal mechanisms
132 have regular properties and behavior^{11,28} but may be moderated by contextual factors, resulting in variable
133 social outcomes¹². A causal mechanism may be intentionally initiated by conservation intervention or may be
134 influenced unintentionally by the establishment, implementation, or cessation of an intervention. By
135 grouping individual causal mechanisms into broad pathways, we do not imply that mechanisms within a single
136 pathway have homogeneous properties (e.g., timing, extent, impact, magnitude), but that each pathway
137 represents a suite of individual mechanisms, which operate via similar social or ecological processes (Table 1).

138

139 Pathways do not operate universally. Specific sets of causal mechanisms may vary substantially according to
140 the attributes of the intervention initiating them¹⁰. The multi-mechanism framework we develop therefore
141 includes attributes that may, depending on context, represent the treatment (i.e., the specific action(s)
142 employed in an intervention), rather than intermediate processes or states in the causal mechanism. To avoid
143 the conflation of treatment and mechanism, the framework must be tailored to the intervention, with
144 attributes of treatment eliminated from analysis of specific mechanisms¹².

145

146 The framework also recognizes three classes of causal mechanisms (following ²⁹): (a) *direct* mechanisms which
147 manifest via social processes linked to an intervention (e.g., reallocation of property rights; ³⁰); (b) *indirect*

148 mechanisms which include one or more ecological processes that impact human well-being (i.e., ecosystem
149 services); and (c) *secondary* mechanisms that result from the interactions among human well-being domains,
150 creating cascading outcomes (e.g., PA impacts on food security influencing school enrollment, ²⁹)

151

152 Mechanisms are subject to both moderation and mediation effects (Table S1). A moderator is a quantitative
153 or qualitative variable that affects the direction and strength of the relationship between a conservation
154 intervention and human well-being. A mediator is an intermediate variable on a specific causal path between
155 treatment and outcome that modifies the functional relationships between variables³¹, reshaping the ‘cogs-
156 and-wheels’ of that mechanism.

157

158 *Governance pathway*

159 The first pathway we identify relates to governance. Governance, “the formal and informal institutions
160 through which authority and power are conceived and exercised”³², fundamentally shapes social-ecological
161 interactions and outcomes. Analyzing governance in the context of conservation is complex³³, in part because
162 it may be a treatment (e.g., PA establishment as a novel governance regime; ³⁴), a mechanism (e.g.,
163 enforcement of resource use rules affecting economic well-being; ³⁰), a moderator (e.g., strict protection
164 versus sustainable use regimes generating different social impacts; ³⁵) and an outcome (e.g. better or worse
165 governance). Here, we concentrate on the role of governance as a mechanism, specifically in relation to
166 decision-making arrangements, property rights, and enforcement.

167

168 Decision-making arrangements are a central feature of governance, with the identity of those able to
169 participate in resource management decisions affecting the magnitude and distribution of an intervention’s
170 social impacts. For example, greater participation in forest management has been associated with improved
171 social and ecological outcomes^{10,36} via incorporation of detailed, site-specific information on resource
172 dynamics into rules considered more legitimate by users and better tailored to local realities ^{10,37}.

173 Participatory decision-making may not always generate positive social impacts, however, as ostensibly
174 participatory institutions fostered through conservation interventions may exacerbate existing gender, caste,
175 and wealth inequalities^{26,38}.

176

177 Conservation interventions often lead to the reallocation of property rights. PA creation, for example, may
178 shift rights relating to who may legally enter the area and exploit its resources³⁴. Such reallocation may
179 disrupt resource use by former rights-holders, but may also boost economic well-being of, for example, local

180 residents, if informal rights to use the resource and exclude others are recognized³⁹. Similarly, payments for
181 ecosystem services schemes can increase land values, which may enable comparatively powerful individuals
182 to exert control at the expense of the less powerful where property rights are insecure⁴⁰.

183

184 Enforcement, the regular monitoring and sanctioning of compliance with rules⁴¹ is central to conservation
185 efforts. It is typically a treatment¹², but can also act as a mechanism, where it may have unintended (positive
186 or negative) social impacts. For example, Kenyan anti-poaching patrols also significantly reduce non-wildlife
187 related crime, including cattle rustling, positively impacting the physical security of local residents⁴².

188

189 *Ideas and information pathway*

190 Conservation interventions may reshape the content and flow of information in a community. The
191 introduction of novel ideas, or the promotion of existing ones often forms a deliberate conservation strategy
192 (e.g., awareness campaigns; ⁴³). Sometimes, however, information-related effects are unintentional. For
193 example, initial exposure to foreign donors through conservation can propel local communities to actively
194 solicit infrastructure development funding¹⁷. Similarly, the presence of non-local staff may influence
195 traditional knowledge systems, facilitating the transmission of ideas between cultures¹⁸. Exposure to novel
196 ideas through conservation may affect behavioral intention, social learning and the likelihood of collective
197 action⁴⁴, shaping the subjective and relational components of human well-being. For example, participation in
198 resource monitoring programs can increase literacy and numeracy among community members, catalyzing
199 secondary impacts on individual and collective empowerment⁴³.

200

201 *Conservation infrastructure pathway*

202 Conservation interventions may trigger one-off or sustained investments in “conservation infrastructure,”
203 which we define as any physical or human capital required to directly support conservation management
204 actions. This includes but is not limited to roads, vehicles, housing, social services, energy and
205 communications networks. In the Congo Basin, for example, the conservation infrastructure necessary to
206 establish a PA network required an initial US \$200 million investment, with recurrent costs of US \$ 3 million
207 per year⁴⁵. While conservation budgets are small compared to other investments⁴⁵ in the region and
208 generally⁴⁶, they may be locally significant, given bias in PA establishment toward marginal regions¹⁵.
209 Conservation infrastructure may also be repurposed by local communities, generating unintended impacts. In
210 northern Kenya, an anti-poaching communications network also served as an informal early warning system
211 against episodic insecurity (e.g., cattle rustling, banditry), increasing physical security. Patrol vehicles have

212 been commandeered as ambulances by community members thereby improving healthcare access⁴².
213 Conservation infrastructure-associated impacts are not uniformly positive. For instance, in Tanzania,
214 conservation personnel resident in isolated PA patrol camps have engaged in high risk sexual behaviors,
215 increasing the risk of HIV transmission in neighboring communities¹⁶.

216

217 *Ancillary opportunities pathway*

218

219 Conservation investments also influence broader social, economic or political processes, providing ancillary
220 opportunities that can change the behavior of actors not directly linked to conservation (e.g. tourism
221 operators, scientists, development agencies). Conservation interventions can transform areas marginal for
222 agricultural production into tourism destinations (e.g., ¹¹), which may bring substantial positive (e.g.,
223 infrastructure development, ¹¹) or negative (e.g. social conflict, ⁴⁷) social impacts. Conservation interventions
224 may also attract visitors with other motivations, with expenditures by visiting researchers, for example,
225 increasing household incomes ⁴⁸ or elevating crime rates⁴⁸ and social conflict⁴⁷.

226

227 Conservation interventions can catalyze investment by state or private sector actors that, for example, spur
228 local or regional “growth poles” that reshapes local economies, affecting the demographics, occupations, and
229 cultural norms^{49,50}. In Namibia, conservation growth poles resulted in outmigration of farmers to urban areas
230 due to fewer agricultural opportunities, and attracted skilled workers to rural villages immediately
231 surrounding PAs⁴⁹. Similarly, conservation growth poles may stimulate higher rates of unplanned
232 development¹⁷.

233

234 *Ecosystem services pathway*

235 The role of ecosystem services in sustaining human well-being is increasingly well-documented^{2,23} but
236 empirical evidence that conservation interventions modify ecosystem services, and that those changes in
237 ecosystem services impact human well-being, remains scarce ²⁶. For example, Costa Rican PAs have had
238 negligible impacts on human well-being via ecosystem services (proxied by land-cover), with the majority of
239 PA-linked poverty reduction attributable to tourism¹². Nevertheless, ecosystem services valuations in the
240 absence of conservation interventions suggest that those which sustain or increase ecosystem services, may
241 substantively impact economic well-being and health^{22,24}.

242

243 **Mediators and moderators**

244 The pathways described in our framework may interact with each other and the context in which they
245 operate, giving rise to a suite of emergent properties. Our framework can help make explicit these emergent
246 properties, which may include novel arrays of synergies and trade-offs, scale-dependency, and distributive
247 effects, that together shape conservation impacts.

248

249 Mechanisms may interact in ways that amplify or dampen the social impacts derived from a single
250 mechanism. These mediation effects may vary over space and time. For example, PA establishment may
251 preferentially reallocate property rights to local fishers, increasing their proportion of total catch³⁰. At the
252 same time, PAs can increase fish biomass³⁹) increasing total catch. In isolation, either mechanism may
253 increase cash income, access to dietary protein, or both, but together may achieve greater impact than either
254 alone. The potential for synergies and trade-offs among mechanisms is widely discussed (e.g.,^{10,26}), but rarely
255 quantified.

256

257 The magnitude and direction of social impacts generated through specific causal mechanisms may be
258 moderated by intervention context⁵¹, pre-treatment levels of the outcome(s) of interest¹², and the social
259 characteristics of affected groups³⁰. Moderators may alter causal mechanisms in predictable or unpredictable,
260 linear or non-linear ways, across multiple scales³¹.

261

262 Conservation interventions can interact with local context to amplify³⁸, dampen or even reverse broader
263 trends in human well-being (Figure 2). Consequently, while a specific causal mechanism may operate
264 consistently across geographies, it may have different qualitative interpretations (e.g., poverty prevention
265 versus reduction;⁶), when viewed in light of other concurrent changes unrelated to the intervention. The
266 moderating role of context is well documented (e.g.,⁵²), but its relative importance versus that of
267 intervention governance is seldom examined quantitatively^{10,53}. Well-managed interventions may overcome
268 unfavorable contextual conditions to deliver positive social impacts³⁶, but fail to do so in others⁵³.

269

270 Moderators linked to demographic characteristics (e.g., age; gender) or social attributes (e.g., wealth; tenure;
271 occupation) can affect either the structure or function of causal relationships³¹. For example, the
272 technologies that fishing households employ shapes PA impacts across multiple social domains, including
273 food security and resource control³⁰ while wealth is frequently associated with disproportionate benefits
274 across intervention types^{26,40}. These distributive effects, when superimposed on pre-existing social gradients
275 and norms, may be equitable or inequitable, amplifying or reversing existing patterns. In Nepal, for example,

276 conservation agriculture has had disproportionately negative impacts on women, exacerbated by underlying
277 gender norms⁵⁴.

278

279 **Spatial and temporal dynamics**

280 Mechanisms may generate impacts that are widespread, concentrated⁴⁹, or display strong directionality⁵⁰. As
281 the socio-ecological processes underpinning mechanisms build or fade over time, the magnitude, direction or
282 distribution of social impacts may also shift, sometimes dramatically. For example, rights reallocation in PAs
283 may generate short-term negative impacts on harvest rates, but these impacts may reverse over time due
284 to biomass increases³⁹.

285

286 **Implications for science and practice**

287 The theory-based framework developed here provides a means to systematically analyze the diverse
288 pathways by which conservation interventions may affect human well-being. It has a number of important
289 implications for sustainability science, policy, and practice.

290

291 *Implications for science*

292 Multiple pathways link biodiversity conservation with human well-being, but sustainability science has largely
293 focused on ecosystem services mechanisms (e.g., ^{23,25}), with comparatively little attention devoted to socially-
294 mediated pathways²⁷. This imbalance in research focus may lead to biased or incomplete understanding of
295 conservation-human well-being linkages. Research efforts should therefore synthesize disparate literatures
296 on mechanisms and generate new empirical evidence on the existence and operation of multiple pathways.
297 Such research may help validate, refine, or expand our classification of pathways and mechanisms. Structured
298 evidence synthesis efforts may shed light on the prevalence and impacts of individual causal mechanisms, as
299 well as hypothesized but under-studied mechanisms. These synthesis efforts will require strong theoretical
300 grounding to guard against concluding some causal mechanisms are unimportant, simply because they are
301 less easily observed (due to the activities or entities involved), or operate at rarely studied scales⁵⁵.

302 Mechanisms with many intermediate states or those operating over very short or long timescales may be less
303 discoverable than those operating on timelines coincident with funding cycles or with few intermediate
304 states⁵⁵.

305

306 Multi-causal and consequential thinking also generates new priorities for empirical research. First, we need to
307 understand the specific social impacts generated by different causal mechanisms, and how these impacts vary
308 between mechanisms. Second, we need to address scale-dependency, given that mechanisms will likely have

309 variable impacts at different spatiotemporal scales and levels of social organization^{49,50}. Third, we need to
310 examine the social-ecological synergies and trade-offs generated by interactions among mechanisms, and
311 understand the feedback generated by such interactions. Finally, within individual pathways, scientific
312 frontiers remain, including for example, the suite of mechanisms linking conservation efforts to subjective
313 well-being⁹. Advancing this research agenda will require broader adoption of impact evaluation methods²⁶ to
314 explore a parsimonious set of potential outcomes, causal mechanisms and moderators^{12,39,56}. Future efforts
315 should adopt analytical approaches that allow the quantification of the relative importance of an individual
316 studied mechanism versus other unstudied mechanisms (e.g., ¹¹), including assessment of how these
317 mechanisms operate across different types of conservation interventions⁵⁷.

318

319 *Implications for policy and practice*

320 Embracing a more holistic framework as proposed in this article has implications for the design,
321 implementation, and monitoring of conservation interventions. The actual impacts of different kinds of
322 interventions may result from a composite of intended and unintended mechanisms, with different
323 characteristics (spatial, temporal or social) than originally planned. Ultimate impacts may also differ
324 substantially in magnitude, direction, equity or domain from those intended. Rather than perceive this
325 complexity as a barrier, multi-causal thinking highlights opportunities to pursue novel implementation
326 strategies designed to exploit multiple mechanisms. For example, maximizing one mechanism (e.g.,
327 conservation infrastructure) could help reinforce positive impacts (e.g., ancillary tourism opportunities) or
328 offset negative (e.g., curtailed property rights) impacts generated by another, while suites of mechanisms
329 could deliver impacts over variable scales or to different social groups. At a minimum, our framework directs
330 attention to potential pathways beyond ecosystem services that may connect biodiversity conservation with
331 human welfare outcomes.

332

333 As public and private funds are mobilized toward achieving the SDGs⁵, adopting multi-causal thinking may
334 generate novel solutions for biodiversity conservation that enhance positive social impacts, or development
335 interventions that deliver ecological gains. Similarly, existing intervention portfolios may be fine-tuned to
336 deliver specific social-ecological impacts valued by local communities thus generating greater incentives for
337 sustainability over time. In so doing, multi-causal thinking enables scholars and decision-makers to better
338 articulate, deliver, and account for the contribution of biodiversity conservation to global sustainability.

339

340 **Methods**

341 We followed standard literature review guidelines⁵⁸ to compile the published empirical studies focused on the
342 causal mechanisms linking biodiversity conservation and human well-being. We located these studies via an
343 iterative search strategy, drawing on published syntheses (e.g.,^{26,30,59}) and online searches via the ISI Web of
344 Science database and Google Scholar. We drew on the disciplinary knowledge of experts participating in the
345 ‘Beyond Protected Areas: Conservation in the 21st Century’ symposium, organized by the authors, at the
346 2012 Association of American Geographers Meeting (24-28 February 2012) to identify relevant literature
347 published in other disciplines. Based on our review of the literature, as well as social-ecological systems
348 theory⁵¹, we iteratively developed the conceptual framework presented here.

349

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494 **Table 1. Illustrative sub-pathways linking conservation interventions with human well-being**
 495

Pathway	Sub-pathway
Governance	Decision-making arrangements Property rights Monitoring and enforcement
Ideas and information	Transmission of ideas Novel ideas Communication channels
Conservation infrastructure	Communications Transportation Energy Personnel Facilities
Ancillary opportunities	Tourism Scientific research Donor exposure
Ecosystem services	Provisioning services Regulating services Cultural services

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500 **Figure 1. Pathways linking conservation interventions with human well-being.** Conservation interventions
 501 (“treatments” illustrated in green) affect one or more human well-being domains (“outcomes” in red) by a
 502 set of causal pathways (“pathways” in blue). Pathways include (a) governance, (b) ideas and information, (c)
 503 conservation infrastructure, (d) ancillary opportunities, and (e) ecosystem services. Impacts may occur
 504 *directly* via one or more social process, *indirectly* via ecosystem services, or generate *secondary effects* on
 505 other human well-being domains.

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509 **Figure 2. Typology of interactions between conservation outcomes and broader contextual trends.** The
 510 outcomes of conservation interventions occur in the context of broader social, economic, political and
 511 environmental trends. The net impact of a conservation is the difference between treatment (depicted in
 512 blue) and control (depicted in grey) outcomes (i.e., change since baseline). An intervention may (a)
 513 *catalyze* an absolute increase, in the context of a broader decline; (b) *magnify* broader increases; (c) *buffer*
 514 against broader declines (less decrease); (d) *mirror* a broader trends (no net impact); (e) *reverse* a
 515 widespread increase, leading to an absolute decrease; (f) *constrain* a broader increase; or (g) *exacerbate* a
 516 broader decrease. Bar height represents relative change in conserved (blue) and similar non-conserved
 517 (grey) areas since conservation intervention establishment. Panels A-B represent positive impacts; D
 518 represents no net impact; and E-G represent negative impacts of conservation interventions.
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522 **Supplementary Materials**

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524 **Table S1. Definitions of key terms**

525 An illustrative example is provided in italic type after the definition of each term.

526

Term	Definition
Pathway	One or more individual causal mechanisms that operate via similar ecological or social processes or share higher-tier properties (e.g., a functional relationship to the intervention itself). <i>Example: Governance</i>
Mechanism	Causal mechanisms are the specific process by which an intervention causally affects a specific social or ecological variable, via one or more intermediate variables ^{12,28,60} . <i>Example: Re-allocation of property rights</i>
Mediator	An intermediate variable on a specific causal path between treatment and outcome that modifies the functional relationships between variables ³¹ , reshaping the ‘cogs-and-wheels’ of that mechanism. <i>Example: Enforcement of reallocated property rights</i>
Moderator	A quantitative or qualitative variable that affects the direction, and strength of the relationship between a conservation intervention and human well-being. <i>Example: Occupation of household head</i>

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